

UWB Nodes Auto-Calibration through a Bias-Aware Two-Stage Methodology*

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Abstract—Ultra-wideband (UWB) technology is gaining acceptance in short to medium-range wireless positioning applications for indoor and GNSS-denied environments due to the accuracy that can be achieved. For this to happen, UWB-based localization requires some knowledge about the underlying infrastructure of network nodes: if the nodes positions are known, one can apply triangulation techniques to self-localize inside the operation area by means of several range measurements with the network nodes. This paper describes a novel two-stage methodology aiming at estimating the localization of the UWB nodes by means of a collection of ranges gathered during an initialization/calibration stage. For enhanced calibration accuracy, the methodology models ranges considering both multiplicative and additive biases. The experiments performed have resulted in estimation errors of the nodes positions of around 11-12 cm under non-line-of-sight (NLOS) conditions.

I. INTRODUCTION

The position estimation problem in an open, outdoor environment can be achieved very robustly by means of Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS), such as the Global Positioning System (GPS), as, in such open spaces, these systems experience good signal reception from the constellation of satellites and measured ranges can be used to triangulate one's position. The GPS signal can, however, be strongly disturbed on its way from the originating satellites to the GPS receiver, not only because of the huge distance that has to be traversed but also due to occlusions (of close mountains, natural and urban canyons, large buildings, trees canopies, etc.), mostly due to multi-path effects; this is even worse indoors, where the signal vanishes. These all lead to situations where strong signals from at least 3-4 satellites (ideally 7-8) can be hardly received and the position cannot be determined. These GPS-denied scenarios demand alternative localization technologies and approaches, the so-called *Indoor Positioning Systems* (IPS), i.e. systems that continuously and in real-time can determine the position of an agent under poor GPS signal reception conditions [1]. Several have been developed to date, with different trade-offs concerning accuracy, energy consumption, infrastructure requirements and cost.

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Among the different technologies employed for localization in GPS-denied spaces (infrared, ultrasound, ZigBee, RF-fingerprinting, light, etc.) [2], UWB radio has shown promising performance thanks to: (1) the resilience of UWB ultra-short pulses to frequency-dependent absorption; (2) relatively low cost, and easy deployment and use (as triangulation of measured ranges to the UWB network nodes is still possible); and (3) the ultimate performance which can be achieved, of the order of a few centimeters [3]. In contrast to these characteristics, some important shortcomings still have to be overcome, such as the estimation of the nodes positions.

In [4], Ridolfi et al. systematize and survey much of the work done regarding the simplification of the deployment of UWB systems aiming at self-localization. For a start, they distinguish between *self-calibration* and *collaborative localization*, where the former refers to an automatic procedure that allows anchor nodes to identify precisely their own locations without manual measuring, being the nodes static after calibration, while the second kind of approach addresses the positioning problem without using a fixed infrastructure but tries to self-localize from the surrounding anchors. In this paper, the focus is on the first topic, i.e. global estimation of the geometry of the UWB network. Within this category, among many others: [5] describes an early approach that computes anchors locations for four nodes using the distances between each pair of anchors and imposing some restrictions on the UWB network, namely anchor 0 defines the origin of coordinates, anchor 0 and anchor 1 define the positive X-axis direction and the plane XY is defined by the first three anchors, while [6] is even more stricter as, over the aforementioned restrictions, anchor 2 is required to lie on the positive Y-axis and anchor 3 on the positive Z-axis, and [7], [8] propose other variations that also constrain the positions of the network nodes; [9], on the other side, proposes a two-stage approach without any restriction on anchors placement, and besides adopts an information-maximization approach for improved performance.

The main contribution of this paper is a novel two-stage methodology for the automatic calibration of UWB nodes positions, aiming at facilitating the deployment of the system. This methodology includes the estimation of range biases for enhanced positioning. Both stages are resolved through respective optimization frameworks that make use of ranges collected while travelling around the network nodes.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section II revises basic facts about UWB technology and the main

sources of error; Section III describes the range model adopted and the two stages of the calibration methodology; Section IV reports on the results obtained under both LOS and NLOS conditions; and, finally, Section V concludes the paper outlining some lines of future work.

II. BACKGROUND

A. Basics of UWB

UWB is based on sending ultrashort pulses, typically less than 1 ns, with a low duty cycle, of the order of 1 : 1000, and over multiple bands of frequency simultaneously, from 3.1GHz to 10.6GHz. The short pulse duration of the UWB signal allows it to penetrate walls in buildings and pass easily through equipment and clothing (although metallic and liquid materials can cause signal interference). Moreover, these short-pulse UWB waveforms, due to their high time-resolution, allow measuring delays between RF emission and reception with better than nanosecond accuracy, making it possible to determine with very high accuracy the *time of flight* (TOF) of a burst transmission from transmitter to receiver, translating into an expected positioning error of a few centimeters [10]. Among the different alternatives [11], this work considers *time of arrival* (TOA) solutions [2] within the segment of TOF-based approaches.

Within a localization framework, an UWB network comprises one or more mobile nodes to be localized and a set of static nodes, respectively named as *tags* and *anchors*. Anchor-to-tag measurements are typically combined by means of multilateration approaches to obtain a position estimate for each tag, provided that the positions of the anchors are known beforehand, either by manual measuring or automatically by self-calibration.

B. Sources of error in measured ranges

The localization performance of a UWB installation is dependent on the quality of range measurements. For this reason, it is important to understand the diversity of factors that can degrade ranging accuracy in UWB. A fundamental challenge of indoor localization is the presence of multipath effects [12], caused by the inherent nature of signals, which can be reflected, refracted, and diffracted not only by the walls (mostly) but also by other elements present in the environment. This fact can affect significantly the behavior of the signals, so that it can get highly unlikely to obtain the direct *line-of-sight* (LOS) signals, and therefore give rise to *non-line-of-sight* (NLOS) conditions under which ranges can temporarily get overestimated.

Another source of error is related with the delays introduced by the hardware involved in the transmission of a UWB signal [13]. This means that the propagation time measured as the difference between the transmission and the reception timestamps includes not only the TOF but also the delay induced by the hardware upward path, i.e. from the circuitry originating the signal to the emitting antenna, and the delay induced by the hardware downward path, i.e. from the receiving antenna to the circuitry decoding the signal. These delays are therefore internal to the chip, can

Fig. 1. a_1 and a_2 are the positions of two anchors of the UWB network and p^t is the position of the tag at time t . r_{12} is the distance from anchor 1 to anchor 2.

vary from anchor to anchor, and have an impact on range measurements [14].

III. CALIBRATION METHODOLOGY

The two-stage methodology that is proposed in this work make use of a set of anchor-to-tag ranges collected while the tag has been travelling throughout the environment during the calibration operation. Moreover, range measurements are assumed to be affected by biases, which are estimated jointly with anchors positions. Hence, anchors models involve both their positions and biases. The first stage adopts a purely geometric approach that obtains a first estimation of anchors positions and biases by means of a regression process. The second stage refines the biases and positions resulting from the previous stage by means of a least squares optimization framework involving a geometric-based regularization term.

A. Range modeling

Ranges \hat{r}_j^t measured at time t by anchor j are assumed to be related with the actual range r_j^t by means of the linear relationship expressed in (1):

$$\hat{r}_j^t = \beta_j r_j^t + \gamma_j \Rightarrow r_j^t = \frac{\hat{r}_j^t - \gamma_j}{\beta_j} = \omega_j \hat{r}_j^t - \delta_j \quad (1)$$

as a compromise between simplicity and accountancy of the behaviour of UWB signal propagation and transceivers (as described in Section II-B). In (1), β_j behaves as a distance dependent, multiplicative bias and γ_j as a constant additive bias, as in [9] (and differently to [14], [15], [16], which do not consider necessary the multiplicative bias).

B. Anchors model estimation

Let us consider the configuration described in Fig. 1, where a_1 and a_2 are the positions of two anchors of the UWB network, and p^t is the position of the tag at time t .

Given the sides of a triangle a , b and c , the *Law of Cosines* states that $c^2 = a^2 + b^2 - 2ab \cos \alpha$, being α the angle between the sides whose lengths are a and b . Hence, according to Fig. 1, we can state:

$$\begin{aligned} r_{12}^2 &= (r_1^t)^2 + (r_2^t)^2 - 2 r_1^t r_2^t \cos \alpha^t \\ &= (r_1^t)^2 + (r_2^t)^2 - 2 r_1^t r_2^t \frac{(p^t - a_1)^T (p^t - a_2)}{r_1^t r_2^t} \\ &= (r_1^t)^2 + (r_2^t)^2 - 2 (p^t - a_1)^T (p^t - a_2) \\ &= (r_1^t)^2 + (r_2^t)^2 \\ &\quad - 2 (p^t)^T p^t + 2 (p^t)^T a_1 + 2 (p^t)^T a_2 - 2 a_1^T a_2 \quad (2) \end{aligned}$$

We now consider two time instants t_1 and t_2 , and the corresponding positions of the tag p^{t_1} and p^{t_2} , together with the respective ranges $r_i^{t_j}$, $i \in \{1, 2\}$ to refer to anchors 1 and 2 and $j \in \{1, 2\}$ to refer to the two time instants t_1 and t_2 . Removing the T superscript to simplify the notation (keeping in mind the corresponding dot products), we can then write:

$$r_{12}^2 = (r_1^{t_1})^2 + (r_2^{t_1})^2 - 2(p^{t_1})p^{t_1} + 2(p^{t_1})a_1 + 2(p^{t_1})a_2 - 2a_1a_2 \quad (3)$$

$$r_{12}^2 = (r_1^{t_2})^2 + (r_2^{t_2})^2 - 2(p^{t_2})p^{t_2} + 2(p^{t_2})a_1 + 2(p^{t_2})a_2 - 2a_1a_2 \quad (4)$$

From the combination of (3) and (4), we can state:

$$2(p^{t_1} - p^{t_2})a_1 + 2(p^{t_1} - p^{t_2})a_2 + (r_1^{t_1})^2 + (r_2^{t_1})^2 - (r_1^{t_2})^2 - (r_2^{t_2})^2 = 2\|p^{t_1}\|^2 - 2\|p^{t_2}\|^2 \quad (5)$$

Moreover, using (1), we can now incorporate measurement biases into (5):

$$2(p^{t_1} - p^{t_2})a_1 + 2(p^{t_1} - p^{t_2})a_2 + (\omega_1 \hat{r}_1^{t_1} - \delta_1)^2 + (\omega_2 \hat{r}_2^{t_1} - \delta_2)^2 - (\omega_1 \hat{r}_1^{t_2} - \delta_1)^2 - (\omega_2 \hat{r}_2^{t_2} - \delta_2)^2 = 2\|p^{t_1}\|^2 - 2\|p^{t_2}\|^2$$

which results into equation (6):

$$2(p^{t_1} - p^{t_2})a_1 + 2(p^{t_1} - p^{t_2})a_2 + ((\hat{r}_1^{t_1})^2 - (\hat{r}_1^{t_2})^2)\omega_1^2 + ((\hat{r}_2^{t_1})^2 - (\hat{r}_2^{t_2})^2)\omega_2^2 - 2(\hat{r}_1^{t_1} - \hat{r}_1^{t_2})\delta_1 - 2(\hat{r}_2^{t_1} - \hat{r}_2^{t_2})\delta_2 = 2\|p^{t_1}\|^2 - 2\|p^{t_2}\|^2 \quad (6)$$

Equation (6) can be stated in matrix form as $A^{(1)}\theta = b^{(1)}$ with:

$$A^{(1)} = \begin{bmatrix} 2\Delta p^{(1)}, & 2\Delta p^{(1)}, & (\hat{r}_1^{t_1})^2 - (\hat{r}_1^{t_2})^2, & (\hat{r}_2^{t_1})^2 - (\hat{r}_2^{t_2})^2, \\ & & 2(\hat{r}_1^{t_2} - \hat{r}_1^{t_1}), & 2(\hat{r}_2^{t_2} - \hat{r}_2^{t_1}) \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\theta = [a_1, a_2, \omega_1^2, \omega_2^2, \delta_1, \delta_2]^T$$

$$b^{(1)} = 2\|p^{t_1}\|^2 - 2\|p^{t_2}\|^2$$

and $\Delta p^{(1)} = [p^{t_1} - p^{t_2}]^T$ for the pair of time instants #1, i.e. pair (t_1, t_2) .

Now, considering n pairs of time instants (t_{i1}, t_{i2}) we can stack the corresponding equations $A^{(i)}\theta = b^{(i)}$ as follows:

$$\begin{bmatrix} A^{(1)} \\ A^{(2)} \\ \vdots \\ A^{(n)} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} a_1 \\ a_2 \\ \omega_1^2 \\ \omega_2^2 \\ \delta_1 \\ \delta_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} b^{(1)} \\ b^{(2)} \\ \vdots \\ b^{(n)} \end{bmatrix} \equiv A\theta = b \quad (7)$$

This can be expanded to take into account not only anchors 1 and 2 but any pair of anchors i and j , what allows considering in a single formulation m the anchor positions and the corresponding biases by defining θ as:

$$\theta = [a_1, a_2, \dots, a_m, \omega_1^2, \omega_2^2, \dots, \omega_m^2, \delta_1, \delta_2, \dots, \delta_m]^T$$

and correspondingly redefining $A^{(i)}$ and $b^{(i)}$ in (7) so as to accommodate the extended set of unknowns.

The vector of unknowns θ can now be found by means of a linear regression model:

$$\theta = \arg \min_{\theta^*} \|A\theta^* - b\|^2 \quad (8)$$

whose solution is well known to be given in terms of the pseudo-inverse A^+ as $\theta = (A^T A)^{-1} A^T b = A^+ b$.

Experimentally, one can see that this regression problem exhibits a number of local minima that can prevent the accurate estimation of anchors positions. To address that issue, one can modify problem (8) incorporating domain knowledge that is reasonably easy to provide: (a) assuming the height of every anchor z_i , $i \in [1, m]$, has been roughly estimated during the deployment of the UWB network by measuring the distance to the floor z_i^h , and (b) assuming the parameters of the range model as stated in (1) are such that $\beta \approx 1$ and $\gamma \approx 0$. Both assumptions can be introduced into the optimization strategy by means of a regularization term as expressed in (9):

$$\theta = \arg \min_{\theta^*} \|A\theta^* - b\|^2 + \lambda_b \left[\sum_{i=1}^m (z_i - z_i^h)^2 + \sum_{i=1}^m (\omega_i^2 - 1)^2 + \sum_{i=1}^m \delta_i^2 \right] \quad (9)$$

where λ_b is a (regularization) parameter of the optimization strategy of the first stage, which balances the relevance of the deviations in equations (6) against the differences with expected values for z_i , β_i and γ_i [in the regularization term of (9)]. In this latter regard, notice that, given the definitions in (1), $\beta \approx 1$ and $\gamma \approx 0$ both mean $\omega^2 \approx 1$ and $\delta \approx 0$.

C. Refinement of anchors positions and biases

Once problem (9) has been solved, the calibration methodology that is proposed in this paper makes use of the resulting anchor models as the point of departure for a non-linear least-squares approach aiming at refining the solution found:

$$\theta = \arg \min_{\theta^*} \sum_t \sum_{i=1}^m (\|p^t - a_i\| - r_i^t)^2 \quad (10)$$

$$= \arg \min_{\theta^*} \sum_t \sum_{i=1}^m (\|p^t - a_i\| - (\omega_i \hat{r}_i^t - \delta_i))^2$$

where, in this case:

$$\theta = [a_1, \dots, a_m, \omega_1, \dots, \omega_m, \delta_1, \dots, \delta_m]^T$$

To overcome again the problem with local minima, this second stage adopts an optimization strategy that also introduces domain knowledge into the process. On the one side, the height of the anchors and the biases are constrained as already done for the first stage, although on this occasion this is implemented by means of lower and upper bounds in the corresponding variables, unlike problem (9). On the other side, perpendicularity relationships that may exist between the planes where the anchors may lie are incorporated into a regularization term, so that refined anchor positions are

expected to keep fulfilling these relationships (this is a reasonable sort of constraint provided the localization problem takes place in a structured environment). The latter set of constraints are implemented by enforcing the perpendicularity between the planes defined by triplets of anchors, whose unit normal vectors can be calculated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} &\text{given a triplet } p \text{ of anchors } i, j, k, \\ &\text{define } \vec{u} = a_i - a_j, \vec{v} = a_i - a_k \\ &\quad \vec{n}_p = (u \times v) / \|u \times v\| \end{aligned}$$

Now, in order to account for all the aforementioned, the least squares problem for the second stage is stated as:

$$\theta = \arg \min_{\theta^*} \sum_t \sum_{i=1}^m (\|p^t - a_i\| - (\omega_i \hat{r}_i^t - \delta_i))^2 + \lambda_{\perp} \frac{1}{|\mathcal{P}|} \sum_{(p,q) \in \mathcal{P}} \vec{n}_p \cdot \vec{n}_q \quad (11)$$

$$\text{subject to } z_i \in z_i^{\text{true}} \pm \Delta z, \beta_i \in 1 \pm \Delta\beta, \gamma_i \in \pm \Delta\gamma, \forall i$$

where $(p, q) \in \mathcal{P}$ refers to pairs of triplets of anchors whose supporting planes are known to be approximately orthogonal to each other, so that their dot product $\vec{n}_p \cdot \vec{n}_q \approx 0$, and λ_{\perp} is the regularization parameter that, during the optimization process, balances the relevance of deviations in ranges with deviations in the perpendicularity relationships. $|\mathcal{P}|$ is the number of elements in \mathcal{P} .

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

A. Setup

For testing purposes, this work has made use of the publicly available benchmark CYBERZOO¹ [17]. This benchmark comprises flight data collected in the *Cyberzoo* testing area at the Aerospace Faculty of TU Delft using a Crazyflie 2.1 aerial platform fitted with the UWB-based LOCO positioning system (which uses the Decawave DWM1000 chip), both by Bitcraze. Groundtruth data (MAV motion and UWB anchors positions) are available through an Optitrack motion capture system. UWB ranges were collected at 100 Hz for a total of 24 datasets on 6 different trajectories (square, triangle, octagon, hourglass, five-pointed star and random sequence, see Fig. 2). For each trajectory, the authors recorded four runs, two in the *two-way ranging* (TWR) mode and two in the *time-difference of arrival* (TdoA) mode, both available from the LOCO UWB system; in this study, only the runs captured in the TWR mode are used. In any case, the UWB network of the CYBERZOO benchmark includes eight beacons enclosing the testing area, located at the positions reported in Fig. 3.

To properly check the performance of the calibration methodology proposed, this paper reports results for two sorts of experiments along the next sections:

- First, the performance resulting for noisy LOS conditions is reported in Section IV-B. To this end, the true ranges for the CYBERZOO benchmark have been

reconstructed at every position of the tag using the available ground truth data, i.e. the true anchors positions and the true motion data captured by the Optitrack system. These ranges have been randomly altered using per-anchor noise, which has been modeled following a Gaussian distribution $N(\mu_e, \sigma_e)$, with μ_e as the mean and σ_e as the standard deviation of the noise, as proposed in [17], [18] for LOS conditions.

- Secondly, NLOS conditions are considered in Section IV-C by directly processing the anchor-to-tag ranges included in CYBERZOO. By way of example, Fig. 4 plots true ranges against measured ranges for one of the anchors in one of the datasets. As can be observed, several ranges were supplied for the same true range by the involved anchor, including both infra- and over-measurements, what corresponds to the multi-path effects that arise under NLOS.

In all tests, regarding the parameters of the two stages of the calibration methodology:

- 1) As for λ_b in (9), it is set according to $\lambda_b = \lambda_B^2 N$, where N is the number of residuals involved in (8), and hence includes all pairs of time instants and all pairs of anchors finally considered², and $\lambda_B = 1500$, being this a setting that has given rise to reasonable performance in general terms.
- 2) Referring to (11), $\Delta z = 0.05$ (m), $\Delta\beta = 0.01$ and $\Delta\gamma = 0.05$ (m). The former is a reasonable uncertainty value for height rough estimations during anchors deployment, while the two latter settings give rise to the upper and lower bounds for the values typically attained by β and γ in (1) for the ranges observed during the experiments performed.
- 3) Finally, regarding λ_{\perp} in (11), in the next sections, it is set up at specific values for testing purposes.

B. Estimation results under LOS conditions

Table I reports on the average error for the anchor position estimates for different amounts of range noise and the 12 datasets (one per column), starting from noiseless ranges up until reaching $\mu_e = 20$ cm and $\sigma_e = 5$ cm, what represents errors between 5 and 35 cm (i.e. $\mu_e \pm 3\sigma_e$). Errors are reported separately for each axis as e_x , e_y and e_z , and jointly through the norm of the error vector (e_x, e_y, e_z) . The rightmost column is the average of the previous 12 columns for each kind of error. In all cases, the regularization term of (11) was unnecessary, i.e. $\lambda_{\perp} = 0$.

The following observations can be made from the results obtained:

- The estimation error is exactly zero for zero noise, while it increases in general as the amount of noise gets higher, both results as expected.
- For the worst noise case considered, the average error gets around 8 cm in X and Y, 3 cm in Z, and 12 cm for the average norm of the error vector (e_x, e_y, e_z) .

²In the different tests performed using the CYBERZOO datasets, N took values of the order of 4000-8000.

¹<https://doi.org/10.4121/14827680>

Fig. 2. Trajectories followed by the tag for 6 of the 12 datasets. (Datasets 2, 4, 6, 8, 10 and 12 are similar to those of resp. datasets 1, 3, 5, 7, 9 and 11.)

Fig. 3. True anchor positions.

Fig. 4. Example of real-to-measured ranges for anchor 7 (dataset 1).

C. Estimation results under NLOS conditions

While the noise on TWR measurements can be assumed to be Gaussian for LOS cases, under NLOS conditions the UWB signals tend to arrive with delay compared to the shortest path, giving rise to heavy-tailed noise distributions due to the multi-path effects. This makes possible not only slightly overestimated anchor-to-tag distance measurements but also severe deviations, i.e. outliers. By way of example, Fig. 5 plots the ranges supplied by one of the anchors in one

Fig. 5. Ranges supplied by anchor 1 (dataset 1).

of the runs, where several outliers can be clearly detected. In order to get rid of those outliers before applying the calibration methodology, we impose an *auto-regressive* (AR) model on the sequence of ranges obtained from the same anchor, i.e. current and near past ranges are linked within the sequence:

$$r^t = \sum_{k=1}^p \varphi_k r^{t-k} + \varepsilon_t \quad (12)$$

where $\varphi_1, \dots, \varphi_p$ are the parameters of the AR model, and ε_t is white noise. The purpose is to detect severe deviations in range measurement that violate the fact that the position of the tag cannot change drastically from one time instant to the next. In the experiments reported, $p = 4$.

Table II shows the same kind of information reported in Table I, although in this case for several values of the regularization parameter λ_{\perp} of (11). Lowest errors for each dataset are highlighted in bold face. From the table, we can conclude that:

- The regularization term is necessary and effective, as $\lambda_{\perp} = 0$ gives rise to the worst performance in all cases.
- $\lambda_{\perp} = 200$ tends to lead to the best or very close to the best performance in all cases. $\lambda_{\perp} = 500$ also leads to the highest performance in a number of cases, as well as $\lambda_{\perp} = 100$, all of which suggests that values of the order of hundreds are the most appropriate.
- Certain variability in the magnitude of errors can be observed across datasets, ranging from e.g. around 10 cm to 15 cm in the norm of the error vector (for $\lambda_{\perp} = 200$). This suggests that certain paths can lead to more accurate anchor positions estimates than others.
- The lowest average error in X is around 6 cm (around 4 cm for some datasets), in Y is less than 10 cm (6-8 cm for some datasets), in Z is below 5 cm (this could be expected) and the average norm of the error vector is around 12 cm (about 10 cm or less for some datasets).

Complementary to the previous data, Fig. 6 plots the estimates obtained for the anchors positions for both stages of the methodology using each dataset separately and $\lambda_{\perp} = 200$. As can be observed, after stage 1, position estimates are around the true positions, while, after stage 2, all positions have converged to the true position within the error margin that has already been reported in Table II.

To finish, the results of a last calibration experiment are reported in Fig. 7. In this case, the 12 datasets have been put together as if they were a single dataset, which has been

Fig. 6. Anchors positions estimates ($\lambda_{\perp} = 200$): (left) after stage 1, (right) after stage 2 ('x': true anchor positions, 'o': anchor positions estimates, different colours for different datasets).

anchor	x	y	z	β	γ
1	-4.48	-4.76	+1.11	1.005	-0.050
2	-4.82	+4.64	+0.72	0.990	-0.049
3	+4.79	+4.67	+0.86	0.990	-0.049
4	+4.89	-4.63	+1.01	0.990	-0.049
5	-4.46	-5.00	+2.56	0.990	-0.049
6	-4.82	+4.37	+2.60	0.990	-0.049
7	+4.54	+4.73	+2.54	0.998	-0.049
8	+4.90	-4.64	+2.50	0.990	-0.049
avg error	0.039	0.093	0.045	avg norm = 0.110	

Fig. 7. Estimates of anchors models using all datasets as a single run ($\lambda_{\perp} = 200$): (top,left) after stage 1, (top,right) after stage 2, (bottom) estimated positions and biases, and average errors in the last row.

processed by the calibration methodology. As shown, the final average error attained in X is less than 4 cm, around 9 cm in Y, 4.5 cm in Z, and the average norm of the error vector is 11 cm.

V. CONCLUSIONS

A simple calibration methodology for UWB networks has been described. It comprises two stages, where the first stage adopts a purely geometric approach from which first estimates of anchors models are obtained, which are refined in a second stage. The results obtained show an average error of 11-12 cm in the estimates of the anchors positions. These results also show a certain variability in the accuracy of the estimations depending on the path followed by the tag during the calibration, what suggests a future line of work consisting in planning a path that can lead to higher accuracy. A second task to be addressed would be the development of an on-line solution inspired in the same principles but able

to calibrate the anchors simultaneously with the estimation of the odometry of the agent carrying the tag, e.g. an aerial robot.

REFERENCES

- [1] Y. Gu, A. Lo, and I. Niemegeers, "A Survey of Indoor Positioning Systems for Wireless Personal Networks," *IEEE Communications Surveys Tutorials*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 13–32, 2009.
- [2] F. Zafari, A. Gkelias, and K. K. Leung, "A survey of indoor localization systems and technologies," *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials*, vol. 21, no. 3, pp. 2568–2599, 2019.
- [3] A. Cazzorla, G. De Angelis, A. Moschitta, M. Dionigi, F. Alimenti, and P. Carbone, "A 5.6-ghz uwb position measurement system," *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement*, vol. 62, no. 3, pp. 675–683, 2013.
- [4] M. Ridolfi, A. Kaya, R. Berkvens, M. Weyn, W. Joseph, and E. D. Poorter, "Self-calibration and collaborative localization for UWB positioning systems: A survey and future research directions," *ACM Computing Surveys*, vol. 54, no. 4, 2021.
- [5] K. C. Cheok, M. Radovnikovich, P. Vempaty, G. R. Hudas, J. L. Overholt, and P. Fleck, "UWB tracking of mobile robots," in *Proc. IEEE International Symposium on Personal, Indoor and Mobile Radio Communications*, 2010, pp. 2615–2620.
- [6] M. Hamer and R. D'Andrea, "Self-calibrating ultra-wideband network supporting multi-robot localization," *IEEE Access*, vol. 6, pp. 22 292–22 304, 2018.
- [7] A. Vashista, A. Gupta, and C. L. Law, "Self calibration of the anchor nodes for UWB-IR TDOA based indoor positioning system," in *Proc. IEEE World Forum on Internet of Things*, 2018, pp. 688–693.
- [8] C. Martinez-Almansa, W. Shule, J. P. na Queralta, and T. Westerlund, "Autocalibration of a mobile UWB localization system for ad-hoc multi-robot deployments in GNSS-denied environments," in *Proc. ICL-GNSS*, 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/TIERS/uwb-drone-dataset>
- [9] J. Bluemel, A. Fornasier, and S. Weiss, "Bias compensated UWB anchor initialization using information-theoretic supported triangulation points," in *Proc. IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation*, 2021, pp. 5490–5496.
- [10] H. Liu, H. Darabi, P. Banerjee, and J. Liu, "Survey of wireless indoor positioning techniques and systems," *IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man and Cybernetics, Part C (Applications and Reviews)*, vol. 37, no. 6, pp. 1067–1080, nov 2007.
- [11] A. Alarifi, A. Al-Salman, M. Alsaleh, A. Alnafessah, S. Al-Hadhrami, M. Al-Ammar, and H. Al-Khalifa, "Ultra wideband indoor positioning technologies: Analysis and recent advances," *Sensors*, vol. 16, no. 5, p. 707, 2016.
- [12] D. Dardari, A. Conti, U. Ferner, A. Giorgetti, and M. Z. Win, "Ranging with ultrawide bandwidth signals in multipath environments," *Proceedings of the IEEE*, vol. 97, no. 2, pp. 404–426, 2009.
- [13] Decawave Ltd, "APS014 Application Note – Antenna Delay Calibration of DW1000-based Products and Systems, v1.2." [Available online https://www.decawave.com/wp-content/uploads/2018/10/APS014_Antenna-Delay-Calibration_V1.2.pdf], 2018.
- [14] A. D. Preter, G. Goysens, J. Anthonis, J. Swevers, and G. Pipeleers, "Range bias modeling and autocalibration of an uwb positioning system," in *Proc. IEEE International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation*, 2019, pp. 1–8.
- [15] A. De Preter, J. Anthonis, J. Swevers, and G. Pipeleers, "Experiment design for ultra-wideband sensor node calibration," in *Proc. IEEE International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation*, 2018.
- [16] S. Monica and G. Ferrari, "Improving UWB-Based Localization in IoT Scenarios with Statistical Models of Distance Error," *Sensors*, vol. 18, no. 5, 2018.
- [17] S. Pfeiffer, C. Wagter, and G. Croon, "A computationally efficient moving horizon estimator for ultra-wideband localization on small quadrotors," *IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters*, vol. 6, no. 4, pp. 6725–6732, 2021.
- [18] A. R. Jimenez Ruiz and F. Seco Granja, "Comparing ubisense, bespoon, and decawave UWB location systems: Indoor performance analysis," *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement*, vol. 66, no. 8, pp. 2106–2117, 2017.

TABLE I
 ERRORS IN ANCHOR POSITIONS ESTIMATES UNDER LOS CONDITIONS
 (FOR SEVERAL LEVELS OF GAUSSIAN NOISE $N(\mu_e, \sigma_e)$ AND THE 12 DATASETS)

Error in x (e_x , meters)

μ_e / σ_e	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	avg
0.00 / 0.00	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
0.00 / 0.02	0.011	0.011	0.012	0.010	0.006	0.009	0.012	0.009	0.007	0.010	0.018	0.007	0.010
0.00 / 0.05	0.043	0.021	0.016	0.022	0.021	0.018	0.016	0.028	0.028	0.020	0.039	0.025	0.025
0.10 / 0.02	0.029	0.033	0.030	0.025	0.016	0.022	0.031	0.026	0.033	0.029	0.019	0.016	0.026
0.10 / 0.05	0.042	0.035	0.041	0.038	0.040	0.027	0.044	0.037	0.048	0.040	0.043	0.030	0.039
0.20 / 0.02	0.075	0.082	0.073	0.075	0.050	0.043	0.073	0.074	0.069	0.077	0.049	0.056	0.066
0.20 / 0.05	0.080	0.088	0.097	0.079	0.080	0.073	0.081	0.103	0.098	0.093	0.083	0.074	0.086

Error in y (e_y , meters)

μ_e / σ_e	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	avg
0.00 / 0.00	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
0.00 / 0.02	0.012	0.007	0.009	0.013	0.006	0.012	0.011	0.006	0.009	0.008	0.019	0.005	0.010
0.00 / 0.05	0.024	0.026	0.013	0.016	0.020	0.017	0.041	0.020	0.026	0.020	0.031	0.026	0.023
0.10 / 0.02	0.028	0.030	0.029	0.025	0.018	0.026	0.019	0.031	0.025	0.028	0.018	0.021	0.025
0.10 / 0.05	0.045	0.053	0.041	0.042	0.035	0.028	0.046	0.044	0.044	0.038	0.037	0.032	0.040
0.20 / 0.02	0.066	0.069	0.072	0.078	0.047	0.044	0.080	0.076	0.070	0.074	0.046	0.049	0.064
0.20 / 0.05	0.092	0.098	0.092	0.094	0.084	0.074	0.070	0.092	0.087	0.092	0.072	0.076	0.085

Error in z (e_z , meters)

μ_e / σ_e	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	avg
0.00 / 0.00	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
0.00 / 0.02	0.013	0.015	0.024	0.009	0.007	0.016	0.011	0.015	0.020	0.013	0.033	0.026	0.017
0.00 / 0.05	0.033	0.031	0.013	0.033	0.031	0.035	0.035	0.022	0.029	0.031	0.034	0.027	0.029
0.10 / 0.02	0.015	0.010	0.014	0.015	0.018	0.022	0.014	0.032	0.022	0.020	0.036	0.025	0.020
0.10 / 0.05	0.034	0.036	0.032	0.009	0.041	0.041	0.006	0.021	0.025	0.019	0.036	0.038	0.028
0.20 / 0.02	0.020	0.021	0.016	0.016	0.015	0.020	0.028	0.017	0.022	0.016	0.024	0.013	0.019
0.20 / 0.05	0.027	0.025	0.033	0.038	0.041	0.031	0.025	0.031	0.026	0.019	0.028	0.032	0.030

Norm of the error vector (e_x, e_y, e_z) in meters

μ_e / σ_e	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	avg
0.00 / 0.00	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
0.00 / 0.02	0.021	0.020	0.028	0.018	0.011	0.022	0.020	0.018	0.024	0.018	0.042	0.027	0.022
0.00 / 0.05	0.059	0.045	0.025	0.042	0.043	0.043	0.056	0.041	0.049	0.042	0.060	0.045	0.046
0.10 / 0.02	0.043	0.046	0.044	0.038	0.030	0.041	0.039	0.052	0.047	0.045	0.045	0.036	0.042
0.10 / 0.05	0.070	0.073	0.066	0.058	0.067	0.057	0.064	0.062	0.069	0.058	0.067	0.058	0.064
0.20 / 0.02	0.102	0.109	0.104	0.109	0.070	0.065	0.112	0.107	0.101	0.108	0.072	0.076	0.095
0.20 / 0.05	0.125	0.134	0.138	0.128	0.123	0.108	0.110	0.141	0.134	0.132	0.114	0.111	0.125

TABLE II
 ERRORS IN ANCHOR POSITIONS ESTIMATES UNDER NLOS CONDITIONS
 (FOR SEVERAL VALUES OF λ_{\perp} AND THE 12 DATASETS)

<i>Error in x (e_x, meters)</i>													
λ_{\perp}	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	avg
0	0.320	0.310	0.380	0.380	0.247	0.231	0.460	0.396	0.341	0.302	0.205	0.211	0.315
1	0.263	0.263	0.332	0.344	0.231	0.211	0.074	0.313	0.281	0.259	0.200	0.193	0.247
10	0.109	0.133	0.181	0.189	0.136	0.117	0.148	0.126	0.112	0.115	0.175	0.180	0.143
100	0.059	0.068	0.109	0.091	0.080	0.071	0.104	0.075	0.054	0.063	0.087	0.056	0.076
200	0.041	0.069	0.080	0.048	0.062	0.058	0.057	0.090	0.070	0.041	0.048	0.070	0.061
500	0.085	0.094	0.073	0.113	0.123	0.094	0.106	0.119	0.092	0.129	0.181	0.189	0.117
<i>Error in y (e_y, meters)</i>													
λ_{\perp}	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	avg
0	0.155	0.160	0.177	0.170	0.144	0.120	0.219	0.155	0.136	0.161	0.154	0.163	0.160
1	0.115	0.144	0.165	0.175	0.145	0.134	0.076	0.143	0.137	0.155	0.154	0.149	0.141
10	0.158	0.178	0.187	0.194	0.173	0.155	0.151	0.174	0.157	0.174	0.171	0.159	0.169
100	0.115	0.116	0.140	0.137	0.123	0.117	0.149	0.123	0.109	0.119	0.085	0.078	0.118
200	0.079	0.100	0.108	0.101	0.109	0.096	0.095	0.111	0.135	0.113	0.054	0.059	0.097
500	0.084	0.068	0.090	0.141	0.102	0.100	0.085	0.100	0.077	0.089	0.151	0.159	0.104
<i>Error in z (e_z, meters)</i>													
λ_{\perp}	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	avg
0	0.050	0.050	0.050	0.050	0.050	0.040	0.049	0.050	0.045	0.050	0.042	0.047	0.048
1	0.041	0.036	0.042	0.037	0.038	0.043	0.032	0.035	0.046	0.044	0.050	0.049	0.041
10	0.049	0.049	0.049	0.049	0.049	0.049	0.049	0.045	0.049	0.049	0.049	0.049	0.048
100	0.046	0.048	0.047	0.049	0.048	0.047	0.046	0.045	0.044	0.045	0.050	0.048	0.047
200	0.049	0.041	0.040	0.044	0.045	0.045	0.045	0.045	0.046	0.049	0.049	0.048	0.046
500	0.045	0.045	0.045	0.045	0.045	0.045	0.045	0.045	0.045	0.045	0.045	0.046	0.045
<i>Norm of the error vector (e_x, e_y, e_z) in meters</i>													
λ_{\perp}	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	avg
0	0.359	0.353	0.422	0.419	0.290	0.264	0.512	0.428	0.370	0.346	0.260	0.270	0.358
1	0.290	0.302	0.373	0.388	0.275	0.254	0.111	0.346	0.316	0.305	0.258	0.249	0.289
10	0.198	0.228	0.264	0.275	0.225	0.201	0.217	0.220	0.199	0.214	0.250	0.245	0.228
100	0.137	0.143	0.184	0.172	0.154	0.145	0.187	0.151	0.129	0.142	0.131	0.108	0.149
200	0.101	0.128	0.140	0.120	0.134	0.121	0.120	0.150	0.159	0.130	0.088	0.103	0.124
500	0.128	0.125	0.124	0.186	0.166	0.144	0.143	0.162	0.128	0.164	0.240	0.252	0.164